
EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION - VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT GRANT 2021

Guidelines for **Meeting Organisers** of Virtual COST Meetings

Date Created: 24th September 2021

This article/publication is based upon work from COST Action < CA17127 Building on scientific literacy in Evolution towards scientifically responsible Europeans >, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).
www.euroscitizen.eu

Authors:

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Please note – meetings and the budget for the moderation support (Local Organiser Support) need to be approved by the MC and COST before being planned

Zoom Account Login Details	1
Potential moderators	1
At least 20 days before the event	1
At least 15 days before the event	1
At least 1-2 days before the event	2
After the event	2

Zoom Account Login Details

Will be provided by the respective WG leader as and when needed

Potential moderators

A list of potential moderators is being assembled. However, please feel free to engage any moderator you prefer. Please make sure to contact them well in advance. It is your responsibility to enroll a moderator that suits your needs (language/availability/costs).

At least 20 days before the event

- Meeting with the Moderator
- Agreement* on the following:
 - Dates and times for the moderation services
 - Hourly rate
 - Date and time for the briefing discussion

*for a template agreement please see Annex A

For additional suggestions about setting up Zoom events, including avoiding/dealing with Zoombombing/trolls please refer to the document 'Instructions to set up Zoom events'.

At least 15 days before the event

- Inform the Moderator and Grant holder (GH) Manager about the following details:
 - Meeting title
 - Date(s) and Time(s)
 - List of participants to be invited through eCOST (this has to be done by the GH Manager)

- Estimated moderation costs

At least 1-2 days before the event

- Meet with the Moderator and brief them on the details of the event
- Make sure they understand the timeline and technical requirements of the event (zoom settings, breakout rooms, polls etc.)
- Decide the timeline for the reports and recording links being made available to you.

After the event

- Make sure you obtain the reports and links to the recordings and make them available to the EuroScitizen community. Please check Annex C and D.
- Approve invoice from Moderator and make sure it is submitted to GH Manager within 15 days

Annex A

EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION

Agreement

Between (*insert name of Meeting Organiser*), hereafter called Meeting Organiser

And (*insert name of Moderator / Moderator Institution*); hereafter called Moderator

The Moderator agrees to moderate a virtual/hybrid event for the COST Action CA17127 at the following conditions:

Meeting title:

Meeting date(s) & time(s):

Estimated number of hours:

Hourly rate in Euros:

The briefing meeting will take place on (at least one full day before the actual meeting):

In order to be reimbursed, the Moderator agrees to comply with all requirements as set forth in the “EuroScitizen – Guidelines for Moderators of Virtual COST Meetings” and confirms that they can legally issue an invoice.

Place, Date

Meeting Organiser

Place, Date

Moderator

Annex C

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Zoom recordings and reports – detailed instructions

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These screenshots have been taken from the EuroScitizen Zoom account. Depending on the zoom account you are using, the pathway to locate the reports might be different.

Recording files

The screenshot shows the Zoom Cloud Recordings interface. On the left is a navigation menu with 'Recordings' highlighted. The main area is titled 'Cloud Recordings' and includes filters for date (From: mm/dd/yyyy, To: 09/24/2021) and status (All Status). There are search fields for ID, meeting number, and audio transcript, along with 'Search' and 'Export' buttons. Below are 'Delete Selected' and 'Delete All' buttons. A table lists recordings with columns for Topic, ID, Start Time, and File Size. Two recordings are visible: 'EuroScitizen SSI transversal meeting' (ID: 822 5663 3745, Start Time: May 25, 2021 02:23 PM, File Size: 3 Files (1.09 GB)) and 'Teste' (ID: 899 0908 1272, Start Time: May 25, 2021 11:20 AM, File Size: 3 Files (31 MB)). Each row has 'Share...' and 'More' buttons.

Generating reports

The screenshot shows the Zoom Usage Reports interface. On the left is a navigation menu with 'Account Management' expanded and 'Account Settings' highlighted. The main area is titled 'Usage Reports' and 'User Activity Reports'. It lists several report types with descriptions: 'Daily' (Show daily number of new users, meetings, participants and meeting minutes in a month.), 'Active Hosts' (View meetings, participants and meeting minutes within a specified time range.), 'Inactive Hosts' (Show the users who are not active during a period.), 'Upcoming Events' (View upcoming meetings and webinars.), 'Meeting' (View registration reports and poll reports for meetings.), 'Cloud Recording' (View detailed information about cloud storage usage by host.), and 'Remote Support' (View in-meeting support sessions during a certain period.).

Participants

Reports - Usage Reports - Active Hosts Document

From: 09/23/2021 To: 09/24/2021 Search

Maximum report duration: 1 Month
 Reports show information for meetings that ended at least 15 minutes ago.

By Meetings By Users Report Queue

[Export as CSV File](#) [Generate details report](#) [Toggle columns](#)

Topic	Meeting ID	User Name	User Email	Department	Group	Has Zoom Rooms?	Creation Time	Start Time	End Time	Duration (Minutes)	Participants	Source
WG3 group meeting	891 9540 2073	EuroScitizen COST Action	euroscitizen@gmail.com			No	07/13/2021 12:48:44 AM	09/23/2021 10:04:29 PM	09/23/2021 10:11:21 PM	7	4	Zoom

Meeting Participants

Export with meeting data Report to Zoom Export

Name (Original Name)	User Email	Join Time	Leave Time	Duration (Minutes)	Guest
Tanja Adnadević		09/20/2021 11:59:47 AM	09/20/2021 12:52:53 PM	54	Yes
Johan (HGUT)		09/20/2021 12:01:04 PM	09/20/2021 12:20:16 PM	20	Yes

Registration, poll, survey reports

Reports - Usage Reports - Meeting Document

Meeting Report Report Queue

Report Type ● Registration Report ○ Poll Report ○ Survey Report

Search by time range From: 09/23/2021 To: 09/24/2021 Search

Maximum report duration: 1 Month

<input type="checkbox"/>	Scheduled Time	Topic	Meeting ID	Generate
<input type="checkbox"/>	09/24/2021 02:30:00 PM	WG5	869 5091 9755	Generate

Processing Reports:

- Download csv file and convert to Excel
- Clean Excel file as follows:
 - Sort by Name
 - Delete unique names that only participated one minute
 - Calculate the total number of participants
 - Prepare layout as per annex D
 - Convert to PDF

Annex D

